

Participant ID	Education	Occupation
P1	MA - CS	Senior Software Developer
P2	MA-CS	Other role
P3	MA-Non-CS	Software Developer
P4	MA-CS	Other role
P5	BA-CS	Software Developer
P6	BA-CS	Software Developer
P7	BA-Non-CS	Software Developer
P8	BA-CS	Senior Software Developer
P9	MA-CS	Software Developer
P10	MA-CS	Senior Software Developer
P11	BA-CS	Software Developer
P12	MA-CS	Senior Software Developer

Terms:

Education:

MA-CS	Master's Degree, computer science or equivalent field
MA-Non-CS	Master's Degree, field that is not computer science or equivalent
BA-CS	Bachelor's Degree, computer science or equivalent field
BA-Non-CS	Bachelor's Degree, field that is not computer science or equivalent

Occupation:

Senior software developer	Occupied as a software developer, participant themselves describes being in a senior position
Software developer	Occupied as a software developer, participant does not describe being in a senior position
Other role	Participant is occupied in a role, that is not primarily a software developer role, but includes software development tasks